

Results

Effect of Serotonin in Planarian Foraging Behavior

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Abstract. Serotonin is a neurotransmitter that has a profound impact on mood and hunger. It is a typical “happy hormone” that is used to treat depression and can also suppress appetite. The study is set to determine the difference in foraging behavior of two planarians, *Paucumara* sp. (marine water species) and *Dugesia* sp. (freshwater species) in the presence and absence of Serotonin. The two species are placed in two different concentrations of serotonin, and pork liver paste is used as a food source to attract the two species. Their corresponding foraging behavior is observed and noted. The results of the experiment showed that there is a positive correlation between foraging behavior and concentration of serotonin for *Paucumata* sp. but not for *Dugesia* sp.

1. Introduction

Serotonin is a neurotransmitter that is widely distributed among the plant and animal kingdoms. Serotonin's precursor, 5-hydroxytryptophan (5HTP), is synthesized by the amino acid tryptophan with the enzyme tryptophan hydroxylase [1]. In humans, serotonin plays a major role in regulating appetite, mood, and circadian rhythms [2]. Serotonin can suppress appetite by increasing insulin secretion, which induce satiation; Serotonin is also considered as a "happy hormone" as it is closely linked with mood stabilizing, meaning that an undersupply of serotonin can lead to depression; Lastly, serotonin is also linked with sleep-wake circulation by signaling hypothalamus [3]. However, recent discoveries of serotonin's effect on invertebrates remain limited.

Paucumara sp. (marine water species) and *Dugesia* sp. (freshwater species) are two species of planarians that belongs to the phylum of flatworms, or Platyhelminthes. Planarians' size ranges from about 3 to 12 mm, including two eyespots symmetrical on the dorsal side of its spade-shaped head, and sometimes have tentacles [4]. Planarians lack body cavity, which is responsible for respiratory and circulatory systems, but do contain simple digestive tract and nervous system.

The digestion system in planarians consists of a mouth, pharynx, and an intestine. After digestive enzymes are secreted, the mouth will begin sucking in food particles. The food will then pass through the pharynx, which connects the mouth with intestine, and enters the intestine (Fig. 1). The cell in the intestine absorbs nutrients from the digested food and diffuse the nutrients throughout the body [5].

Figure 1. The digestive and nervous system of planarian [6].

There is a basic nervous system in planarians as well. The nervous system contains a cerebral ganglion, transverse nerves, and ventral nerve cords (VNC) located on the side of the body (Fig. 1, adopted from [6]). From the central brain, or ganglion, the two transverse nerves extend to the end of the tail and connect to the VNC on the opposite sides to make a ladder

shaped nervous system. This structure of the nervous system will make the planarian act more coordinately and comprehensively [7].

There have been previous studies done on the effect of serotonin on flatworms. Some research data indicated that the amount of serotonin would influence the motor control system of invertebrates, such as muscles and parasitic flatworms [8-10]. The result of these studies showed that the examined flatworm species has at least one motor control based on a serotonin receptor. Some sources indicated an inverse effect of serotonin on feeding behavior for invertebrates [11-12]. Despite these advances of knowledge, many complex and mechanisms related to serotonin remain unknown, including some of the foraging behaviors of *Paucumara* sp. and *Dugesia* sp. Therefore, the experiment was conducted to test the effect of different concentrations of serotonin to the foraging behavior of two planarian species. The results identify serotonin as an effective pheromone that triggers active foraging behavior in *Paucumara* sp. but has limited effects on the foraging pattern of *Dugesia* sp.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Planarian Species Sampling

The two planarian species *Paucumara* sp. and *Dugesia* sp. were all raised in the lab condition. *Paucumara* sp. was raised in salt water and *Dugesia* sp. was raised in fresh water. For both species, around 500 flatworm specimens were maintained in an aquarium with running freshwater/20ppt seawater. The flatworms were fed with pig liver homogenate with a daily amount of no more than 1g.

2.2. Neurotransmitter Solution And Food Source

Serotonin precursor, 5-hydroxytryptamine (5HT), was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Sigma-Aldrich, U.S.A). Lyophilized 5HT powder was firstly dissolved in 0.1M HCl. A 10-1 M stock solution was prepared. To prepare the working concentration (10^{-3} M), the stock solution was diluted for 100 times. The dilution process required 1mL of stock solution and 99ml of freshwater/20ppt saltwater, which produces a 100mL working serotonin solution. The solution was then put in a 100ml plastic test tube and kept at 4 degrees Celsius to ensure the normal functions of serotonin.

The pork liver was used as a food source to attract the planarian species. Approximately 100 grams of fresh pork liver were bought in supermarket and grinded into paste using a set of mortar and pestle. The pork liver paste was then transported into a sealed plastic bag to keep the food source from factors that can damage the food quality such as humidity and microbial degradation.

2.3. Control Group

Freshwater and 20ppt sea water were poured into a 50ml graduated cylinder. Then 15ml of both water samples were poured into separate petri-dishes with the diameter of 7cm. Both *Paucumara* sp. and *Dugesia* sp. were extracted from the aquarium by a pipette and pumped into corresponding conditions (*Paucumara* sp. in 15ml salt water and *Dugesia* sp. in 15ml fresh water). Approximately 1g of pork liver paste was taken from the plastic bag by a pair of tweezers and placed in the center of the petri-dish. The petri-dish for each specie was placed under an inferred microscope in a dark environment and a video filming the petri-dish was taken by a device (phone or computer). The video should be stopped when the planarian has successfully eaten the food, or when the planarian did not move for a long period, approximately 5 or 6 minutes. The movement trail was computed by an in-house developed algorithm, which will be reported elsewhere.

2.4. Experimental Groups

Freshwater and 20ppt salt water were poured into a 50mL graduated cylinder. Measure 14mL and 13mL of each water sample and pour them into four separate petri-dishes. A micropipette was then used to remove corresponding amounts of serotonin taken from the refrigerator into each of the petri-dishes to generate a final solution of 15mL. Experimental group one and two will have correspondingly 2mL and 1mL of serotonin in 13mL and 14 mL fresh or 20ppt salt water. Use the micropipette to mix the samples evenly so it became a homogenous solution. The solution should be settled to room temperature to match with the same conditions in the control group. The procedures of food placement, video filming, movement trailing should also be the same as the control group.

3. Results

The pictures produced by the algorithm (Fig.2 and Fig.3) represent the foraging route of *Paucumara* sp. and *Dugesia* sp. The letter “S” represented the starting point and letter “E” represented the ending point. The foraging route of the two species was mapped out by a red line. Picture A was the control group, Picture B was experimental group 1, and Picture C was experimental group 2. The length of the red line represents the displacement of the planarians in their foraging route. More displacement traced meant more movements during the foraging time, which indicated an active foraging pattern. In the contrast, less displacement marked out on the figure indicated less movements, demonstrating an inactive foraging behavior.

The preliminary experiment was conducted on July 14th, 2022. The results suggested that the most direct foraging behavior occurred in *Paucumara* sp. in experimental group 2 which 2mL of serotonin is added (Fig. 2), while experimental group 1 showed the greatest movements during foraging (Fig. 2). Along with the data of *Paucumara* sp. foraging behavior in experimental group 1 (Table. 1), the result implicated a potentially positive relationship

between the amount of serotonin added and the number of foraging behaviors in *Paucumara* sp. as all *Paucumara* sp. experimental groups expressed active eating behavior in serotonin solutions (Fig. 2, Table 1).

Control Groups	
<i>Paucumara</i> sp.	Climb up the wall of petri-dish, not attracted to food, but the mouth is reached out (around 12-20min)
<i>Dugesia</i> sp.	Do not eat food but wonders around
Experimental Group 1	
1ml 5HT/Serotonin added	
<i>Paucumara</i> sp.	Approach the bait several times and wonders around. Bait eaten
<i>Dugesia</i> sp.	First wonders around, then settled on the dish wall. Doesn't eat the bait.
Experimental Group 2	
2ml 5HT/Serotonin added	
<i>Paucumara</i> sp.	Approach bait in very short time. Stay at the bait for the rest of the time. Bait eaten
<i>Dugesia</i> sp.	Wonders around the dish, not eating the bait

Table 1. Simple experimental logs taken along the experiment.

Figure 2. The foraging route of *Paucumara* sp.

A. The control group. B. Experimental group 1. C. Experimental group 2. The letter “S” represented the starting point and letter “E” represented the ending point. The foraging route of *Dugesia* sp. was mapped by a red line.

Figure 3. The foraging route of *Dugesia* sp.

A. The control group; B. Experimental group 1; C. Experimental group 2. The letter “S” represented the starting point and letter “E” represented the ending point. The foraging route of *Dugesia* sp. was mapped by a red line.

However, there seemed to be limited correlation between the foraging behavior of *Dugesia* sp. and the amount of serotonin added. *Dugesia* sp. in the control and two experimental groups did not eat the bait, and less activity of *Dugesia* sp. was observed in the solution with 2mL 5HT. (Fig. 3)

4. Discussion

The results from the experiment appear to match some research indicating an inverse effect of serotonin in invertebrates^[11]. Instead of suppressing appetite, the increasing serotonin level increase the foraging behavior in *Paucumara* sp. However, the results also indicated a lack of effect of serotonin on *Dugesia* sp. The lack of reaction in *Dugesia* sp. with the present of serotonin might imply that *Dugesia* sp. did not contain a serotonin receptor, or the threshold for *Dugesia* sp. to sense serotonin presence is higher than the one for *Paucumara* sp.

The latter explanation might be plausible since the marine planarian, *Paucumara* sp. should be more sensitive to pick up *neuroligands* since it’s genetically suited for exposure to complex and dangerous marine environment that contained numerous ligands. Some possible ligands such as omega-conotoxin (omega-CgTx) GVIA^[15,16] and paralytic shellfish toxins (PSTs)^[17,18] were neurotoxins that would cause poisoning to *Paucumara* sp. Therefore, picking up

the right ligand by developing a more complex neurotransmitter sensing system for *Paucumara* sp. would be crucial for survival. However, there was a lack of pre-exposure to numerous signals as it was in a more stable freshwater system. Therefore, the neuroligand sensitivity in *Dugesia* sp. would not be as sensitive as the one in *Paucumara* sp., meaning that it would not respond in 1 or 2mL of serotonin in a 15mL solution.

This study was important because it can be further analyzed to determine complex and more thorough function of serotonin in both vertebrates and invertebrates, which might be implanted to treat some parasitic planarians such as tapeworms and flukes^[9,13,14].

Some possible sources of error in this experiment might come from sampling and insufficient experimental data. Different individuals of planarians from both species in aquarium had different levels of physical health, satiation, and were in different stages of development. Perhaps one individual of *Dugesia* sp. was very active in foraging, while another individual simply adhered to the wall of petri-dish and reach out its mouthpiece to obtain small food particles in the solution. Another error could be the error of randomization. Since all the groups in the experiment were simply tested once, there could be a significant risk that the data obtained was only based on a coincidence. Further improvements such as repeating the experiments and testing different concentrations of serotonin could be made to gain more accurate data.

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